

WAYS TO ADAPT A YOUNG ORGANISM TO PHYSICAL EXERCISES

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Annotation

This article shows the problems of ways to adapt a young organism to physical exercises

Key words

Process, feature, development, exercise, in physical education, result, physical qualities, sports, knowledge, physical culture, physiology, adaptation

The young organism tries to adapt to the influence of the external environment in every possible way. When the body has its own laws of natural development, such as exercises that are complex to perform or physical exercises intended to perform in the long run, or when mastering the technical and tactical aspects of sports in the process of training, simple to complex, easy to difficult pedagogical principles are used, it is easier for a young organism to adapt to such situations. Skills and competencies are not formed at once in a young organism, since the long-term performance of one exercise is formed by the method of repeated over and over again. Observations in this regard show a number of results. In particular, when we control the results of athletics in long-distance running with children aged 11-12 it is noticeable that most children could not reach their destination, that is, the finish. In this, young children show that qualities such as willpower, endurance, physical qualities are not well developed. In Physical Culture and sports circles, complex exercises are performed with students.

However, due to the fact that in the process of physical education, special exercises are not carried out step by step, regularly, students have low results from physical education. As the growing young organism develops in terms of its structure, it corresponds to the physical development of older children. Physical qualities such as strength, willpower, flexibility, dexterity are present in a person by nature, but it is on the responsibility of teachers of unconditional, physical culture to further develop these physical qualities in the body, to ensure its adaptation to physical exercise.

Because every physical culture and sports specialist should know the characteristics of a young organism, for this he should master the disciplines of

anatomy, physiology, pedagogy, psychology, sports metrology, biomechanics, theory of physical culture well. Only then will he be able to fulfill the tasks that he has set for himself. Otherwise, the growing and developing organism can be brought to a state of braking. In practice, such situations also occur that, although the child's appearance is extremely developed, he cannot perform physical exercises well in the process of sports training. Or he has difficulty doing long-lasting exercises. What are these consequences? We came to the conclusion that this is, of course, the result of the fact that in the process of Physical Culture training in secondary schools, the structure of a young organism is not taken into account its physical development and their ability, what it is capable of. To prevent this, teachers of Physical Culture and sports coaches will have to be constantly sought on themselves, organize practical training at the required level by deepening theoretical knowledge.

In this, one thing must be taken into account that the young organism responds to the influence of the external environment, it tries to develop at a rapid pace in every possible way, for which it will have a predisposition. In this case, the athlete must regularly prepare his body with the help of physical exercises. Adaptation to the external environment and physical exercises, unconditionally, depends on the development and physical fitness of the organism of young children.

In the process of physical development, the heart rate of children increases. In general, the children's blood circulation system ranges from 65 to 85-90 per minute between the ages of 7 and 17. This indicator will depend on the respiratory and excretory organs in some children. Children living in different areas have different heart strokes because children living in mountainous areas are different from those living in temperate lowland areas.

Physical exercises are elementary movements, States of movement compiled from them and their complexes, elements systematized for the purposes of physical development. In the practice of physical education, physical exercises, mastered from the daily labor, domestic, military activities of a person (running, walking, jumping, ironing, lifting weights, swimming, etc.) and organized and methodically formalized as, athletics and weightlifting, action and sports games, sports tourism, etc., will be built on the basis of actions and circumstances.

Before starting the main part of the exercises (exercises that are performed in the order of continuous rhythmic movements, before moving on to exercises), it is necessary to write for 5-10 minutes, that is, perform much lighter physical

exercises first. The exercises performed while writing the can also be, by their type, the same as when the main part is performed; they differ only in intensity. For example, a slowed down walk — before running, is seen as a type of exercise that is performed as a writing log. It allows you to develop skills in increasing physical loads on the heart muscle and other muscles, as well as on the lungs and joints. In addition, writing a tick or warming up muscles and joints can help prevent possible injuries. After writing the chisel, it is necessary to carry out a practical relaxation of the muscles.

The main part is made up of exercises performed in the order of continuous rhythmic movements. Their benefit is that they have a beneficial effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory system. In the process of performing these exercises, large groups of muscles are launched, which, at the expense of increased oxygen flow, provide the energy potential that will be needed to perform them in a certain necessary time. As a result, lactic acid build-up does not occur, as in anaerobic (a condition in which no air is present) exercises.

The goal of this phase of the exercise is to strengthen the cardiovascular and respiratory system. Table of contents of the exercise program (selection of exercises). it will depend on the physical condition of a person at the same moment, on the features and personal preferences of his lifestyle. The criteria below serve as a specific guide to developing a personal exercise program) repetition (frequency).

The frequency (frequency) of repetitions of exercises is determined by the number of exercises within the week. In order to improve your general physical condition and maintain an optimal body weight, it is necessary to yourself with physical education at least 3 times a week; it is necessary that the break between any two exercises in the urine does not exceed two days. At the beginning of your exercise program, it is better to do it 3 times a week (alternating days) for 4-6 weeks. For example, it can be Monday, Wednesday and Friday or Tuesday, Thursday and Sunday. You will then be able to increase the frequency of training to 4-6 days a week.

Under the concept of consistency, it is accepted to understand the number of movements (physical strength) that are spent at the core of the exercise. The degree of consistency will depend on the initial general level of physical fitness, and it also depends on what goals the person sets for improve health and disease prevention or, for example, increase the vital cow of the lungs (OHS), people who do not have sufficient physical fitness from the start are advised to start training at the lowest level of intensity.

Pulse stroke (number of heart contractions) - is an indicator of acceleration during exercise. The purpose of the exercise is to conduct the training at such a high level that it is equal to the pulse rate at the physical load, or the pulse frequency at the exercise. The duration of time or exercises consists of the number of minutes spent on physical exercises that are performed by force. If the speed level is not high, it is necessary to increase the duration of the exercise, and if, on the contrary, the speed of the exercise is high enough, it will be possible to reduce its duration for a while. For example, if a person is driven by constant physical labor (Carpenter, farmer or builder), he can achieve a "practiced effect", even in the case when the infection is not large, because in practice he spends every day with movement. In a situation that occurs mainly with people who sit and work, the rate of increase in physical loads and should be much higher, so that it can achieve the "practiced effect". This is how, the faster the exercise becomes, the less time is spent on it, and vice versa. For individuals who do not have sufficient physical fitness, it is recommended to start their exercise program 4-6 days a week for 10-15 minutes, those with an average level of training — 20-30 minutes, and those with good physical fitness — 30-60 minutes.

Most of the adaptive reactions of the human body are carried out in two stages: the initial stage of urgent but not always perfect adaptation and the next stage of perfect, long-term adaptation. The urgent stage of adaptation occurs immediately after the onset of the effect of the stimulus on the body, and it can be carried out only on the basis of previously formed physiological mechanisms. Examples of the manifestation of urgent adaptation are: passive increase in heat production in response to cold, increased thermal conductivity in response to heat, increased pulmonary ventilation in response to lack of oxygen, and minute volume of blood circulation. At this stage of adaptation, the functioning of organs and systems continues at the limit of the physiological capabilities of the body, with almost complete mobilization of all reserves, but does not provide the most optimal adaptive effect.

Adaptive nature occurs at the organ level: the speed of blood flow increases, blood pressure rises, the breathing volume of the lungs increases, breathing accelerates, breathing deepens) and the body as a whole. The general adaptive reactions of the body are not specific, that is, the body responds in the same way in response to the actions of various stimuli in terms of quality and strength (exercise).

Resistance associated with adaptive reactions of the body and muscle

activity. The body maintains the relative dynamic stability of the internal environment necessary for life, although it responds to the influence of many variable external and internal factors. This reaction is the main way of adaptation, adaptation of life. Each of the factors used is characteristic of quality and quantity. The quality of a stimulus distinguishes this stimulus from others, determines the specifics of its action. The quantity of a stimulus, a measure of its biological activity, is something in common that is specific to any stimulus, defining an uncharacteristic aspect of its effect on the organism.

Muscle load is no exception. With muscle load, as with the action of any stimulus, the body undergoes a series of specific changes and develops an uncharacteristic reaction associated with a quantitative measure of the load. Of course, the concepts of "quantity", "measure", "strength", "dose" in relation to the body are very relative. The degree of biological activity of the active factor is determined not only by the absolute value of this factor, but also by the sensitivity of the body to it.

In relation to muscle load, this is of particular importance, since with the help of exercises it is possible to control the sensitivity and resistance of the body to it. A well-trained athlete can carry such a muscle load, which will be very large for those who are not trained. Nevertheless, each person treats the load differently depending on the change in its value, the principle of quantitative and qualitative remains: the dependence of the body's response reaction on the amount of load. Thus, the quantitative and qualitative regularity of the development of general nonspecific adaptive reactions was determined: adaptive reactions develop, which differ qualitatively depending on the strength, dosage, biological activity of active factors, external and internal environment of the body.

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